

The Implementation of an Asset-backed Pillar in the Austrian Pension System

Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the potential implementation of an asset-backed pillar within Austria's pension system to address demographic and financial sustainability challenges. Austria's current pension system is under increasing pressure due to demographic shifts, notably an aging population and shrinking contributor base, resulting in escalating federal funding demands. To address these issues, this thesis proposes the introduction of a mandatory funded pillar, striving for a hybrid pension system. Utilizing capital market investments through a defined contribution scheme, this proposal aims to mitigate demographic pressures, enhance retirement income through diversified equity investments, and ensure intergenerational fairness. Empirical evidence, including OECD and recent financial market analyses, supports the viability of increased equity exposure for superior long-term retirement outcomes. Furthermore, a theoretical framework, based on modifications of the pay-as-you-go (PAYG) model from Orszag and Stiglitz (2000, 24ff), demonstrates strategies to minimize transition costs inherent in moving towards a partially-funded system.

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1. Introduction

The sustainability of Austria's pension framework is under increasing strain. Declining birth rates and rising life expectancy have created a demographic imbalance: fewer contributors are supporting a growing population of retirees (Statistik Austria 2024a). As a result, the traditional expectation, that today's workers will finance tomorrow's pensions, faces a looming shortfall.

This thesis argues that introducing an asset-backed pillar alongside Austria's existing system could mitigate not only demographic pressures but also financing issues raised by the tax supplementation, while preserving intergenerational solidarity (Sinn 2000, 402ff). By diverting a portion of contributions into capital market investments, future retirees could benefit from dual income streams, partly financed by younger cohorts and partly by their own accumulated savings. Such a partial funding approach can help prevent the overburdening of today's workers and ensure a dignified standard of living in retirement (Matsen/Thøgersen 2004, 885ff; Jarner et al. 2024, 832).

However, recent market volatility, resulting from crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, the Ukraine conflict and trade tensions during Donald Trump's second term, raised concerns about the viability of funded pension systems. The potential for significant wealth losses among retirees during volatile periods is alarming for both pensioners and policymakers. Moreover, another crucial challenge regarding this topic is to design a scheme in such a way that transition costs are minimized, in order to not overburden the transitioning generation with additional contributions and to yield a fair intergenerational outcome (Sinn 2000, 395ff; Matsen/Thøgersen 2004, 901f; Barr/Diamond 2006, 1ff; Boulhol/Lüske, 2019, 37ff).

The following chapters examine these issues in depth. Chapter 2 introduces the main policy options for pension design, distinguishing among a variety of different pension schemes that are currently in place (Matsen/Thøgersen 2004, 883ff; Barr/Diamond 2006, 1ff; Boulhol/Lüske, 2019, 37ff; Jarner et al. 2024, 813ff; OECD 2024a, 57ff) and summarizing best practices for funded models (World Bank 2008, 1ff; OECD 2017, 87ff, Mercer 2024, 7ff). Chapter 3 describes Austria's current pension system (OECD 2023b, 2ff; DG EMPL/SPC 2024b, 5ff; OECD 2024b, 33ff; BMSGPK 2025, 7ff) and identifies key challenges such as the demographic change and fiscal pressures (Statistik Austria 2024a; Mayrhofer 2025, 1ff). In Chapter 4, a proposal for a hybrid scheme gets developed, including an optimal default asset-allocation strategy for the funded pillar, based on the findings of Anarkulova et al. (2025, 2ff) and the OECD (2024b, 86ff). Resuming with an analysis of the implications of higher equity exposure

(OECD 2024b, 102), in the last part of chapter 4, the proposition of minimizing transition costs follows a modified model by Orszarg and Stiglitz (2001, 24ff). Finally, Chapter 5 concludes with a synthesis of implications, challenges and opportunities for implementing an asset-backed pillar in Austria.

2. Pension Systems

Before starting with formulating the proposal, it is essential to distinguish and review existing pension systems, as well as seeking guidance of designing a funded component in Austria.

2.1 Different Types of Pension Systems

Generally, pension systems can be classified into two different groups: first, how they are organized and second, how contributions relate to benefits. Additionally, the mentioned systems can be further defined by the level of responsibility and the eligibility of beneficiaries (Barr and Diamond, 2006, 4; Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 38).

2.1.1 Organizational Structure

Regarding the organizational structure, the literature considers three main types of schemes, namely fully-funded, partially-funded and pay-as-you-go (PAYG) models (Matsen/Thøgersen 2004, 884ff; Barr/Diamond 2006, 4ff; Boulhol/Lüske, 2019, 38ff; Jarner et al. 2024, 814).

Fully-funded systems are financed by the current contributions of the now working population, where they accumulate a stock of savings, which are then invested into financial assets. These funds and their returns benefit the contributors in their retirement. In theory, pure fully-funded schemes have enough assets available in form of funds to cover their liabilities (Barr/Diamond 2006, 4; Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 38). Naturally, they grew in popularity in recent years, due to the attractive returns associated with financial market investments (Jarner et al. 2024, 818; OECD 2024b, 3). Although appealing, there are inherent risks which exist with this approach, namely no direct redistribution across individuals, the financial constraint of a population's past savings (Barr/Diamond 2006, 4) and the general investment risk and heightened volatility in the short run (Matsen /Thøgersen 2004, 818; Bégin 2020, 58).

The PAYG scheme operates under a different premise: current workers' contributions are used immediately to pay today's retirees. This arrangement rests on an intergenerational "solidarity pact", defined by the states legislation, whereby each cohort of employees, by funding the system today, earns the right to receive benefits tomorrow - benefits that will, in turn, be financed by the subsequent generation of contributors (Barr/Diamond 2006, 4; Boulhol/Lüske

2019, 38; BMSGPK 2025, 7). The PAYG-Model, as it is run today by most of the sovereign states, has its merits regarding redistributing and risk-sharing (Barr/Diamond 2006, 4), but also has its natural flaws, namely lower fertility rates (Jarner et al. 2024, 818).

A partially-funded model takes the previous two models and combines them into a hybrid scheme (Bégin 2020, 58), also called a two pillar or multi-pillar system (Scharfstein 2018, 1471; Jarner et al. 2024, 814). It mitigates many of the risks associated with the pure forms mentioned previously and has other desired effects (Sinn 2000, 402ff; Matsen/Thøgersen 2004, 885), but also additional medium-term costs (Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 37), an issue which this thesis will deal with more in later chapters.

2.1.2 Defining Characteristics of Pension Systems

The aforementioned pension models are essentially distinguished by how contributions translate into benefits. There are three common types of approaches regarding this relation (Barr/Diamond 2006, 5; Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 38):

First, there are Defined Contribution (DC) schemes, where a fixed amount of contributions is invested into individual accounts. These contributions are then invested into financial assets, where they yield a return, which accumulates in these pension accounts. Retirees are eligible to use their own accumulated savings to fund their retirement through annuities or similar methods, depending on legislation and design (Barr/Diamond 2006, 6; OECD 2017, 86; OECD 2018, 143).

Defined Benefit (DB) Schemes are another possibility of financing the retirement period. Here an individual's pension is not defined by account savings, but their wage history. Generally, the individual must contribute a fraction of his or her wage, to earn their future benefits, according to their lifetime earnings, after retiring (Barr/Diamond 2006, 6; OECD 2017, 86).

For the sake of completeness, it is necessary to mention Notional Defined Contribution (NDC) schemes, which resemble DC schemes, but not fully. There are parallels, like the individual accounts and the fixed contributions, but the savings in the accounts only get "notionally" invested. This means that the state sets a notional interest rate, to grow the contributions of an individual over their life. (Barr/Diamond 2006, 7). "Notional" because the account balance only exists for record-keeping on the books of the managing institution (OECD 2017, 86).

Moreover, there is also a different question regarding public, occupational or private schemes, but these are mere characteristics of the before mentioned systems. PAYG Models can be designed to exhibit DB or DC features, while being publicly or privately managed. Italy and Poland have such mixtures, following a public NDC scheme based on a PAYG Model (OECD

2017, 86; Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 38), while Switzerland and the Netherlands have publicly funded DB pensions. Also, PAYG Models must not be managed by the state, as there are occupational or private schemes for example in Germany (Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 38).

2.2 Policy Suggestions for Hybrid Pension Models

As pointed out in the previous chapter, there is a variety of possibilities to design a well-functioning pension system. Bégin (2020, 58) summarizes this ambition, that to find the ideal pension system, policy-makers must be committed to provide a stable environment for four main indicators, affordability, adequacy, sustainability and transparency. Further key objectives, recommended by the World Bank (2008, 1ff), include equitability, predictability and robustness, which are also essential to prevent a shortcoming of future generations.

Adequacy means benefits must reliably prevent old-age poverty and smooth lifetime consumption priorities (Mercer 2024, 18), whereas affordability demands that costs remain within the fiscal and individual capacity without crowding out other (World Bank 2008, 3f). Sustainability requires long-term financial soundness under plausible demographic and economic scenarios (Mercer 2024, 19) and equitability mandates redistribution from lifetime high-earners to low-earners in line with societal norms without additional taxes (World Bank 2008, 4). Transparency and Predictability calls for benefits to be legally specified, inflation- and wage-indexed, and shielded as far as possible from longevity risk (World Bank 2008, 4; Bégin 2024, 58f) and robustness ensures the system can absorb major economic, demographic or political shocks (World Bank 2008, 4). In practice, these criteria interact and sometimes conflict, e.g. low contribution rates may undermine adequacy or sustainability, and country-specific factors, like how elderly health care is financed, shape the optimal trade-offs (World Bank 2008, 3f; Mercer 2024, 7).

The World Bank proposes a five pillar structure, reasoning that a multi-pillar-structure, enhances flexibility to achieve the aforementioned objectives of pension schemes, while guaranteeing a more secure environment. The first pillar, the Basic Pension, delivers a non-contributory, publicly financed benefit, either universal or means-tested, that guarantees a minimum income floor to avert elderly poverty. The second pillar, a Public PAYG model, links contributions to wages and calibrates benefits to replace a specified share of pre-retirement earnings once the statutory retirement age is reached. The third pillar consists of mandatory private DC schemes, either occupational or individual accounts, while the fourth pillar encompasses voluntary DC plans, typically bolstered by tax subsidies to increase retirement savings. Finally, the fifth pillar, informal assets, encompasses personal savings, insurance

products and family or community support mechanisms that smooth consumption and provide care outside the formal pension system (World Bank 2008, 2ff; Mercer 2024, 17).

The OECD has a more general recommendation of constructing pension systems, with only three pillars or tiers (OECD 2017, 86ff): A mandatory, tax-financed first tier for poverty prevention, a mandatory second tier of savings to replace earnings, via public DB, notional DC and private DB/DC, and a voluntary third tier of supplementary DB or DC plans. Together, these layers balance adequacy, income replacement and consumption smoothing while distributing risk among the state, employers and individuals.

While both of these theoretical frameworks merely offer guidelines on how to enhance the individual pension system of a state, they will be used in this thesis to derive a proposal which complements the current Austrian pension system.

3. The Austrian Pension System

After conferring about different types of pension systems, this section is now dedicated to describe the Austrian pension system. There are two subsections, first, the introduction of the organizational structure and description of the system as it is today and second, the depiction of main challenges the Austrian Pension system faces.

3.1 Description

Generally speaking, Austria has a three-pillar pension system as shown in figure 1, consisting of the public PAYG DB scheme, and the occupational and private pension plans, with DC and DB features (DG EMPL/SPC 2024b, 5ff BMSGPK 2025, 7ff).

The most vital part of the Austria pension system is the compulsory, statutory pension scheme, which provides a PAYG retirement benefit for virtually everyone in gainful employment, including self-employed people (DG EMPL/SPC 2024b, 5; BMSGPK 2025, 7ff). The OECD (2023b, 2) characterizes this first pillar as a public DB scheme with an income-tested equalization supplement (“Ausgleichszulage”) for retirees in financial hardship.

Funding for such a pension scheme happens three-pronged: first, through contributions by the working members, in form of “social insurance contributions” (Sozialversicherungsbeiträge), second, by contributions from the employer and third, from tax financing (BMSGPK 2025, 9f). Regarding the first two funding mechanisms, total pension-contribution rate is 22.8% of gross earnings, which means for salaried employees, this is a split into a 12.55% employer share and a 10.25% employee share (BMSGPK 2025, 11). Self-employed individuals pay 18.5%,

with an additional 4.3% “partner contribution” covered by the federal budget (OECD 2023b, 4). Each year, 1.78% of an individual’s gross salary is credited to their notional pension account, up to an earnings cap of 79 380€. Past contributions are indexed in line with overall wage growth, excluding the retirement year and the year immediately prior. Pensions are paid out in 14 installments annually and then adjusted each year roughly in line with consumer-price inflation (OECD 2023b, 4f; BMSGPK 2025, 22ff).

Figure 1: The Austrian Three-Pillar-System (TPS)

Source: BMSGPK 2025, 7ff and DG EMPL/SPC 2024b, 5ff, modified by the author

The second pillar, namely occupational pension schemes, primarily involves multi-employer pension plans using a financial institution model. Here, a pension company or financial intermediary offers plans open to any employer but in Austria, initiating these plans requires a sector-level collective agreement between employers and unions. Employers select a provider and establish a contract, benefiting from economies of scale through pooled contributions (OECD 2024b, 33ff). Such plans, while growing in absolute size and coverage, are but rather secondary for the general population. In 2022, 23.2% of employees were eligible for additional pension benefits from occupational pensions, yet just 7.8% of those over 65 are beneficiaries (DG EMPL/SPC 2024b, 7). These numbers have not changed much over the past years and stayed approximately similar. In summary, 2.9 billion € went to beneficiaries in the year 2023, equivalent to an annuity of 21,177€ per capita (Statistik Austria 2024a, FMA 2024, 4ff).

Individuals can further enhance retirement savings through private pension schemes, the third pillar, e.g. investment-based savings or insurance products. To promote participation, the government introduced subsidized provision plans (“Prämienbegünstigte Zukunftsvorsorge”), offered as annuity insurance policies or pension investment funds (BMSGPK 2025, 63). Still, the impact has been little and few people are actually engaging in such private pension insurances, with declining numbers over recent years (DG EMPL/SPC 2024b, 8).

3.2 Challenges

Before introducing the proposal, it is crucial to comprehend the difficulties of the Austrian PAYG model, namely demographic shifts, rising life expectancy and the escalating federal funding. The following sub-chapter discusses these main challenges, laying the groundwork for a comprehensive redesign of the Austrian pension framework.

3.2.1 Demographic Shifts

Demographic changes create significant challenges for Austria’s pension system. In 2024, the country’s population was 9.17 million, with 1.84 million or 20% aged 65 or older. By 2050, total population is projected to reach 9.83 million, and those 65 and older will comprise 28%, or around 2.75 million in absolute terms (Statistik Austria 2024a). In the same time the population between 20 and 64 year olds experiences a decline from 5.57 to 5.28 million, which means that PAYG financed schemes are in a dire situation, notably the first pillar of the Austrian pension system (Statistik Austria 2024c). In 1950 there were roughly 5.77 people within working age per pensioner, in 2024 there were 3.03 and in 2050 only 1.92 (Statistik Austria 2024a), so the PAYG system experiences a decreasing amount of contributors and an increasing amount of beneficiaries within the statutory pension system.

Additionally, the average life expectancy is projected to rise, further intensifying this demographic challenge. According to the Austrian Pension Commission (ASK 2024a, 24) average life expectancy for men at 65 is expected to increase from 18.4 years in 2023 to 22.7 years in 2050, while women go even from 21.5 to 25.2 years. This development not only means longer payout periods but also underscores the need for structural reforms to sustain the system financially.

3.2.2 Federal Funding

Austria faces increasing tax expenditures (“Bundeszuschuss”) necessary to sustain the pension system. In 2024, total spending on benefits for retirees, including the statutory pension, was 13.1% of Austria’s GDP or 63.5 billion €, of which 88.4% funded first-pillar

pensions (Statistik Austria 2024b, Mayrhuber 2025, 1; Statistik Austria 2025a). By 2029, these expenditures for the pension insurance are expected to climb to 77.2 billion €, and the federal contribution will grow accordingly to maintain financial stability in the pension system (Mayrhuber 2025, 2).

The gap between contributions by active workers and pension payments is increasingly bridged by these federal funds. In 2024, approximately 27% of the total pension expenditures, 17 billion €, had to be covered by federal budgetary means, accounting for roughly 13.5% of the federal budget or 3.5% of GDP (Mayrhuber, 2025, 1ff). On a side note, federal support for Austria’s pension system, which includes both the statutory scheme and civil-service pensions, amounts to about 6% of GDP in 2024, roughly 3.5% for the public insurance system and 2.5% for civil servants (Mayrhuber, 2025, 1). While crucial to acknowledge, for further analysis, this thesis will only mention the federal funding of the first pillar.

Figure 2: Development of the Federal Funding for the Statutory Pension System in Austria

Source: ASK 2024b, 107ff, modified by the author

Figure 2 presents the historical data from 2017 to 2024 and the forecasted development of the necessary federal funding from 2025 to 2029, both in absolute and relative terms. According to this data, between 2020 and 2024, the total federal funding needed for the pension system rose by almost 52% and continues to increase in the years to come (ASK 2024b, 107ff). This is due to the indexation of pensions, which may even have overcompensated pensioners and the lump-sum payments made during the years 2022 and 2023 (OECD 2023a, 64ff; DG EMPL/SPC 2024a, 112ff; BMSGPK 2025, 45f). The latest projections made by the Austrian Pension Commission indicate that federal funding for the statutory pension insurance will peak at roughly 6.5% of GDP by 2060 before stabilizing near 6.2% through 2070, while excluding funding allocations for civil servants and social security and health benefits (ASK 2024a, 181ff).

Moreover, these estimates do not incorporate the Austrian Ministry of Finance's budgetary plans of 2025, suggesting that a revised forecast is needed for greater precision.

In summary, it should be acknowledged that the federal funding of the first pillar via the "Bundeszuschuss" has dramatically increased in recent years and will increase further over the next periods. Furthermore, there are also other pension related schemes which need federal funding, e.g. the partner contribution for the self-employed, survivors benefits, the equalization supplement, which increase the strain on public finances in the years to come, especially in the presence of the high budgetary deficit (Mayrhuber 2025, 2ff; Statistik Austria 2025b).

4. Designing the Hybrid Pension System

Having outlined the existing Austrian pension system, while highlighting its inherent shortcomings, this thesis now proposes a reformed pension scheme grounded in recent literature and scientific consensus. The subsequent chapters will delve into the critical design choices necessary to achieve the objectives set out in Chapter 2.2.

4.1 The Four-Pillar Proposal

Following the guidelines and frameworks provided by the OECD (2017, 85ff) and the World Bank (2008, 1ff), the proposal is a funded pillar which gets added to the three-pillar-system (TPS), therefore making it a four-pillar-system (FPS) and also a hybrid scheme, with funded and unfunded characteristics (World Bank 2008, 2ff; OECD 2017, 87).

This new second pillar is the funded component of this scheme, where, in DC fashion, mandatory contributions are placed in individual accounts and then invested into financial assets (Barr/Diamond 2006, 6; OECD 2017, 86; OECD 2018, 143). The contributions and returns will accumulate over the lifetime period of the becoming retiree which then gets disbursed as retirement income (Jarner et al. 2024, 814). The inspiration for the proposal of the funded component in a multi-pillar framework will be drawn from the work of Matsen and Thøgersen (2004, 884ff) and Jarner et al. (2024, 813ff), as well as from the proposals of the OECD (2017, 87ff) and the World Bank (2008, 1ff). Subsequent chapters will reference additional authors and institutions to refine the pillar's design.

For the sake of completeness, this funded DC pillar, as seen in Figure 3, is depicted in two ways that may require further explanation: First, the quasi-public trait, which describes the fund as a mandatory plan for all individuals in employment, can be also understood in a quasi-

occupational way. This means that every individual in gainful employment between the ages of 25 to 65, a period, which is based on the methodology in the later chapters from the OECD (2024a, 86) and Anarkulova et al. (2025, 10), is mandated to contribute a certain percentage of their income. The eligibility criteria includes in this case also all people in non-standard forms of work, namely self-employed individuals to ensure inclusivity, due to the proposed mandatory enrollment.

Figure 3: Four-Pillar-System (FPS) Proposal for Austria

Source: World Bank 2008, 1ff; OECD 2017, 87; OECD 2023b, 2ff, modified by the author

Second, quasi-occupational is here synonymous with quasi-public, because almost all individuals of a population find themselves in employment during their lifetime period. Furthermore, responsibility of the financial intermediary means that, as already explained in chapter 3.1, financial institutions or pension companies are responsible for the sponsorship of existing occupational plans. (OECD 2024b, 33ff). Now, the underlying fund structure could be managed by a similar, but independent, financial intermediary, created specifically for this purpose, where employers must opt in joining due to this mandatory nature. From a regulatory perspective, it could mirror Austria’s existing “Pensionskassen” framework as established by the Occupational Pensions Act (FMA 2024, 1ff; OECD 2024a, 58; BMSGPK 2025, 61ff).

Importantly, this proposal rests on the assumption that the initial amount of social contributions and taxes are now going to different pillars of the pension schemes, called initial-funded ratio

(IFR) (Matsen/Thøgersen 2004, 901f; Bégin 2020, 70ff). Admittedly, this assumption raises the challenge to overcome transition costs from the original model to the hybrid scheme (Sinn 2000, 395ff; Matsen/Thøgersen 2004, 902; Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 50f; Jarner et al. 2024, 826). This challenge is tackled in a later chapter, following the discussion of the DC plan’s default investment strategy and an analysis of its projected returns.

Table 1: The Two Main Pillars of the proposed Hybrid Pension Scheme

	Pillar 1: DB, PAYG	Pillar 2: DC, Fully Funded
Financing	General taxes or fixed contributions (% of income)	Individual contributions (% of income)
Entitlement	Based on age, residence and wage history	Directly based on one’s own contributions
Returns	Implicit, from wage growth	Market-based returns
Incentives	Weak due to decoupled contributions and benefits	Stronger, especially if tax exemptions are made
Risks	Wage growth, demographics, political decisions	Market performance, regulatory changes, medium-term transition costs
Diversification	Across population and generations	Individual wage earners from 25 to 65, market based diversification
Redistribution	High potential, due to decoupled contributions and benefits	Limited; Rather indirect through taxes in the payout phase

Source: Jarner et al. (2024), 820, modified by the author

Due to the low participation in voluntary occupational and private pension plans, the two last pillars prove to be insufficient for the upholding of a steady consumption rate in the retirement period over a whole generation, as depicted in chapter 3.1 (DG EMPL/SPC 2024b, 7f). While both pillars are noted using FPS terminology for completeness, this thesis focuses on the unfunded PAYG and funded DC components, summarized in table 1 (Jarner et al. 2024, 820), with the interaction of all pillars left for future study. Undoubtedly, there are a lot of details still to unravel and design accordingly, e.g. the amount of contributions, if and how employers and employees are splitting the mandated contributions, the government’s influence, the qualification as an “occupational” arrangement, pay-out phases, the IFR, retirement ages, management of financial markets risk and the amount of transition costs (Matsen/Thøgersen 2004, 902; OECD 2017, 88ff; Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 50f; Jarner et al. 2024, 826). While for some parameters the assumptions are based on the calculations done by the OECD (2024b, 86ff)

and Anarkulova et al. (2025, 2ff), regarding other design choices, this thesis follows only the topics of market volatility and transition costs in detail, mainly because these are the most pressing concerns policy makers have to face (Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 50f), which goes without deeming the other factors as irrelevant. Admittedly, grasping the other parameters is vital for refining this proposition, but should be part of further research.

4.2 Asset Allocation Strategy - An Optimal Portfolio Approach

Essential for designing this new pillar is the underlying funded structure, especially in regard to volatility (Bégin 2020, 59; Bégin/Sanders 2024, 73). Nowadays, members of DC pension plans around the world are more or less responsible for choosing their investment strategy, where options may be overcategorized, e.g. conservative, balanced, dynamic, growth, aggressive, green or ethical (OECD 2020, 102). A default investment strategy, set by policy makers and pension plan designers may be the viable solution for individuals who do not have the thorough conception to choose from a variety of different plans, or, even worse, if their judgement lets them choose too conservatively, only to forego expected retirement income (OECD 2018, 140ff; OECD 2020, 102ff; Gomes et al. 2021, 16ff; Berardi/Tebaldi 2024, 272). Starting out by analyzing the current asset allocations and their real returns over the past years, the following chapters are proposing such a default investment strategy based on the framework by Anarkulova et al. (2025, 2ff).

4.2.1 Asset Allocation and Returns of Funded Pension Plans in Austria

In Austria, at the end of 2023, voluntary occupational and private pension assets totaled just 6.8% of GDP, approximately \$36 billion (OECD 2024a, 11). Figure 4 represents the asset allocation from those voluntary pension plans, which depict a rather conservative aggregate strategy:

Figure 4: Asset Allocation of voluntary Austrian Pension Plans

Source: OECD 2024a, 17, modified by the author

Equities make up only 27.4% of the total investment volume, while the percentage in bonds and bills are almost identical, with 27.9%. Cash and deposits make up around 3.3% and “other assets” account for 41.4%. The “other assets” category includes land, buildings, loans and funds among others, so assets which cannot be classified as equities, bills and bonds, or cash and deposits (OECD 2024a, 17). Austria’s funded pension landscape shows solid asset growth in voluntary private and occupational schemes, but it is their internal rate of return (IRR) that really measure their performance. Although the geometric average nominal growth rate of assets of pension funds was 8.4% in 2023 and over the last 10 years 3.7% and 20 years 5.3% (OECD 2024a, 37), however the real IRR was -0.1% and 0.5% respectively, and 0.6% in 2023 (OECD 2024a, 15). Despite substantial pension plan growth over the past five years, they even recorded a loss in terms of real returns of 1.3% (OECD 2024a, 39), but this is admittedly also due to the high inflationary environment in 2022 and 2023 (Statistik Austria 2025c), which shows however proneness to the overlooked and underestimated trend of inflation in the context of real returns rather than the much more overestimated market volatility (Beradi/Tebaldi 2022, 273). Nevertheless, most voluntary and occupational pension plans pursue relatively conservative strategies, which is why they failed to offset the recent surge in inflation (OECD 2024a, 41).

4.2.2 Default Investment Strategies and Equity Exposure

After analyzing the asset allocation and return expectations of existing pension plans in Austria, selecting from a variety of viable default investment strategies in DC plans comes with the inherent trade-off of offering the highest possible retirement income in the future, while protecting beneficiaries from lower than expected outcomes (OECD 2020, 102).

While an equity-heavy default strategy can boost long-term retirement income, it also brings greater short-term volatility compared to a fixed-income option, which seemingly undermines its role in protecting becoming retirees (OECD 2024b, 76; Anarkulova et al. 2025, 2ff). However, for individuals unable or unwilling to choose an investment strategy, e.g. due to inadequate financial literacy, a default strategy, upon enrollment, implies, on average, lower risks for the beneficiaries (OECD 2018, 140ff; OECD 2020, 102). Also, individuals saving up for retirement using a default option in DC schemes are more likely to remain in this default setting even if it does not match their risk appetite (OECD 2024a, 103).

On a side note, designing a strategy to address this trade-off should not only consider risk factors such as uncertainty about future retirement income, but also parameters including contribution rates, fees, taxation and payout options (OECD 2020, 102). For the subsequent chapters, this thesis assumes each parameter to be aligned to the Austrian model currently in

place, so taxes, contribution rates, fees charged and the annual 14 installments of payout stay the same (BMSGPK 2025, 7ff). Parameter specification beyond this partial-equilibrium proposal is essential, but it falls outside this thesis's scope and is reserved for future research.

4.2.3 The Optimal Default Strategy

Portfolios that include equities tend to generate larger retirement savings than those limited to domestic bonds and cash (Anarkulova et al. 2025, 2ff). In a hypothetical DC scheme modeled across 83 cohorts in 19 OECD countries, including Austria, an allocation featuring even a modest equity component outperformed a portfolio with fixed-income when measured by the ratio of assets accumulated at retirement to total contributions (OECD 2024b, 87).

Methodology-wise, the OECD (2024b, 86) modeled a representative worker who enters the labor market at age 25 and retires at 65. Their wages start out the same for each cohort and grow each year in line with historic inflation plus a constant 1.25% productivity uplift. Over the course of a 40-year career, they contribute 5% of their salary towards a DC scheme and incur a 1% annual asset management fee. Using a block-bootstrap real return method and inflation data for 19 OECD countries from 1900 to 2021, they calculate, for each of the 83 cohorts retiring between 1939 and 2021, the multiple of the accumulated assets at retirement from the total contributions paid by evaluating five different investment approaches:

- 1) **Domestic fixed income (FI)**: 88% government bonds and 12% cash/deposits (using treasury bills as a proxy for cash returns).
- 2) **Diversified equities (E)**: 70% domestic stocks and 30% foreign stocks (with EU equities substituting domestic ones from 1990 onward).
- 3) **Balanced 60/40 portfolio (60/40)**: 60% equities (Half domestic, other half international) and 40% fixed income (bonds and cash/deposits in the same 88/12 ratio).
- 4) **10-year life-cycle glide-path (LC10)**: Starting with 80% equities (70/30 domestic/international), then reduce equity exposure linearly over the final decade of the working life down to 20%, shifting into domestic fixed income.
- 5) **20-year life-cycle glide-path (LC20)**: Same initial 80% equity allocation, but the gradual shift to 20% equity is spread evenly over the last 20 years before retirement.

The calculated average level of assets accumulated in Austria lies approximately between 3 and 11 times the amount of contributions, across all investment strategies, but the four strategies with equity exposure tend to overperform the FI-strategy by at least double the amount. This shows that equity exposure leads to a significantly higher value of assets at the

beginning of the retirement age in comparison to the FI-strategy. Generally speaking, the FI-strategy has multiplies of 1.9 to 3.5 across the 19 observed countries, while the E-Strategy varies between 4.5 to even 11.2, whereas the results of the other approaches tend to fall in-between these two ranges (OECD 2024b, 87).

However, it should be noted, that wartime exchange-rate swings during the World Wars inflated the nominal returns of US-dollar assets when converted into schillings. This effect was most pronounced in the 60/40 portfolio, over half of whose holdings were international, making its past performance look stronger than more domestically focused strategies. (OECD 2024b, 114). This is also shown by the standard deviation for each respective strategy which reaches from a little more than 1.0 with the FI-Strategy to 11.0 with the 60/40-strategy (OECD 2024b, 91). Still, all 83 analyzed cohorts in Austria would have been better off investing in equity markets, instead of investing them into domestic fixed income (OECD 2024b, 89).

A much more general approach was used by Anarkulova et al. (2025, 2ff), where they found, that the optimal investment strategy, for the pre-retirement period of a two people household, is a diversified equity strategy with 33% domestic and 67% foreign equities, yielding \$1.07 million at retirement on average.

Figure 5: Mean Wealth and Standard Deviation at Retirement and Mean Wealth at Death (\$Million)

Source: Anarkulova et al. 2025, 43, modified by the author

Within one million Monte-Carlo simulations, using the GFDatabase from Global Financial Data from 1890 till 2023 for 39 developed countries, this strategy proved itself to be superior in comparison to the other analyzed strategies on average, in regard to the net wealth aggregated at the beginning of the retirement. Furthermore, it also boasts lower standard deviation than the balanced portfolio which is here equal to the 60/40 portfolio defined by the OECD (2024b,

87ff). It also yields higher net wealth at the time of death on average and there is also less risk of exhausting wealth during retirement (Anarkulova et al. 2025, 18ff).

It is important to note, that for interpreting wealth levels, a household consisting of two people in a developed country saves on average \$0.24 million over their lifetime, in this case from 25 to 65 years old (Anarkulova et al. 2025, 19). For completeness, the bills strategy here mirrors the OECD's fixed-income approach, and the TDF strategy follows a life-cycle glide-path (OECD 2024b, 87). Thus, both Anarkulova et al. (2025, 2ff) and the OECD (2024b, 87ff) find that a higher or even complete equity allocation delivers the best retirement outcomes, maximizing net wealth while minimizing standard deviation and portfolio drawdowns.

4.3 The Implications of Higher Exposure in Equities

While higher equity exposure clearly enhances retirement outcomes (Anarkulova et al. 2025, 19), it also introduces new implications for beneficiaries of the proposed pension plan:

First, it should be acknowledged that better retirement outcomes require longer accumulation and contribution phases, so delaying retirement or starting earlier with the contributions are yielding substantially higher benefits in the payout phase. Across all asset-mix strategies, cohorts contributing for 40 years always outpaced a 20-year horizon, with the widest disparity in fully diversified equity portfolios. However, even with just 20 years of contributions, 69% of cohorts across 19 countries would have achieved higher pre-retirement wealth by including equities instead of sticking to domestic bonds (OECD 2024b, 102).

Second, higher equity allocations in DC pension plans tend to produce more variable annual returns and replacement rates than portfolios concentrated in bonds and cash (OECD 2024b, 102; Anarkulova et al. 2025, 40ff). Higher equity volatility increases uncertainty for retirees and can amplify wealth gaps between cohorts with identical earnings and contributions. Although these fluctuations may seem inequitable, it is important to remember that, on average, participants still achieve superior retirement outcomes with an higher equity exposure due to the longer time horizons (OECD 2024b, 102).

Third, pension payouts can be highly vulnerable to a sharp equity drawdowns before and during retirement (OECD 2011, 214; OECD 2024b, 102; Anarkulova et al. 2025, 40ff). In general, literature suggests life-cycle strategies to help buffer this "timing" risk: they maintain heavy equity exposure early on, then steadily shift into fixed income during the final working years (Viceira 2001, 456; Gomes et al. 2021, 22ff). However, their protective advantage diminishes the earlier the downturn occurs, since a longer recovery window reduces the impact on final asset levels (OECD 2024b, 102).

4.4 The Minimization of Transition Costs

As already stated in chapters beforehand, several parameters still need defining, most importantly, the transition costs from the current TPS to the proposed hybrid FPS scheme. (Sinn 2000, 395f; Matsen/Thøgersen 2004, 902; Barr/Diamond 2006, 35; OECD 2017, 88ff; Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 50f; Jarner et al. 2024, 826). To show a theoretical way on how to decrease the adverse effects of transition costs, resulting from the move from an existing PAYG system to a hybrid scheme, the topic of this chapter is a model based off the model introduced by Orszarg and Stiglitz (2001, 25). This model was repurposed to fit a general case of a hybrid-scheme pension system to illustrate the challenge of medium-term costs and to validate the before made proposition. Admittedly, policymakers must weigh these costs alongside the relative risks of each scheme and the administrative expenses of adding a funded component (Barr/Diamond 2006, 30).

To start out, there are 4 time periods, each 40 years long, in which one generation, from the age of 25 to 65, works and pays contributions, while another generation retires, receiving the payment from the working generation. Only two generations are active in each individual period and, with a constant benefit rule in place, the first generation receives exactly as much as was paid in the previous time period, which is 1.0 (Barr/Diamond 2006, 30). Deviating from the original concept, the depicted numbers can be understood as percentages or ratios, e.g. how much of the aggregate contribution of a generation goes towards the pension system or in subsequent cases to which pillar, as well as how much the generation gets paid out as a percentage of their contributions. Additionally, the first two models exclude inflation, while all models exclude increasing productivity and increasing efficiency and population growth or decline. With these assumptions made, the simplified PAYG System looks as follows (Orszarg/Stiglitz 2001, 25):

Table 2: PAYG Model

Period	Generation				Net Welfare
	A	B	C	D	
1	1	-1			0
2		1	-1		0
3			1	-1	0
4				1	0

Source: Orszarg/Stiglitz 2001, 25, modified by the author

Orszarg and Stiglitz (2001, 25) expand this model to represent a funded DC model, with a market interest rate of 10% per period, as shown by table 3. This expansion reveals that the funded DC model has an inherent flaw: As every generation is only contributing into their own

individual accounts, the initial generation A gets no payment, because the contribution of generation B only goes towards their own retirement income, amounting to 1.1 in period 2 (Sinn 2000, 395f; Orszarg/Stiglitz 2001, 25; Barr/Diamond 2006, 30).

Table 3: Funded Model

Period	Generation				Net Welfare
	A	B	C	D	
1	0	-1			-1
2		1.1	-1		0.1
3			1.1	-1	0.1
4				1.1	0.1

Source: Orszarg/Stiglitz 2001, 24f, modified by the author

However, according to the previous chapters, it is evident, that the assumption of only 10% return, over a full career of 40 years, is even with a FI-strategy highly unlikely (Anarkulova et al. 2023, 2ff). The real implicit returns or multiples of contributions presented by the OECD (2024, 87ff), as pointed out in the chapter 4.2.2, suggest other results: The 60/40-strategy may multiply contributions by up to 11.2 over forty years on average, while a pure fixed-income approach tops out at 2.9, so the equivalent gain would be 190% over four decades. For subsequent models, the assumption of the multiplier is based on the optimal strategy for life-time savings, a diversified, all-equity approach, as described in the previous chapters. Although the optimal strategy generates wealth at the beginning of the retirement age equal to 4.458 times the amount of contributions on average, a simplified multiplier of 4 will suffice for this model (Anarkulova et. al 2025, 17).

Table 4: Transition from PAYG to funded DC

Period	Pillar	Generation				Net Welfare
		A	B	C	D	
1	PAYG	0	-1			-1
2	DC		4	-1		3
3	DC			4	-1	3
4	DC				4	3

Source: Orszarg/Stiglitz 2001, 24f, modified by the author

Table 4 shows that moving from PAYG to a funded DC plan raises expected returns for every generation after A, but generation A gains nothing unless later cohorts sacrifice their own contributions. It should be noted that administrative and tax costs for individuals are not included here.

Deviating from the depiction of Orszarg and Stiglitz (2001, 25), the next model tries to depict the made propositions in the aforementioned chapters. Table 5 illustrates the shift from a PAYG to a hybrid scheme with an IFR of 0.5, meaning contributions are evenly split between the

funded component and the PAYG system. Still, even with the multiplier of 4, generation B can fund only half of generation A's benefits, while the contributions in the funded component achieve higher net welfare in every coming period except the first, since excess returns only begin in period 2.

Table 5: Transition from PAYG to hybrid scheme; IFR = 0.5

Period	Pillar	Generation					Net Welfare
		A	B	C	D	E	
1	PAYG	0.5	-0.5				-0.5
	DC		-0.5				
2	PAYG		0.5	-0.5			1.5
	DC		2	-0.5			
3	PAYG			0.5	-0.5		1.5
	DC			2	-0.5		
4	PAYG				0.5	-0.5	1.5
	DC				2	-0.5	

Source: Oszarg/Stiglitz 2001, 24f, modified by the author

Further analysis showcases that however high returns the funded component yields, it is not possible to completely blend out transition costs in the initial period, which comes at the costs of either higher contributions or longer contribution periods for the younger generation or less benefits for the older generation. Still, in either case, the resulting outcome for the transitioning generation is on average better from an intragenerational net welfare perspective, if using the optimal investment strategy (Anarkulova et al. 2024, 18ff), but worse from an intergenerational one. There is a trade-off for the transitioning generation B: forego consumption today to increase consumption potential later in life. So even with a total contribution of 1.5 from generation B, where the generation burdens themselves with paying 1.0 for generation A, while saving 0.5 for themselves, the theoretical outcome of 2.5 should still offset negative welfare accrued in period 1, but raises said questions about intergenerational fairness and equitability (Sinn 2000, 404).

Introducing taxes alters the model's outcomes: In Austria, pension benefits follow the income-tax schedule, while capital gains and dividends incur a special taxation of 27.5% (§ 27a Abs 1 EStG). For simplicity, assuming a 25% tax on 2.0 of accumulated assets generates 0.50 in tax revenue, which can be used for other distributional means. In period 1, Generation B pays 0.5 into the PAYG scheme, incurs an extra 0.5 contribution (Extra Cont.), to cover Generation A's benefits, and saves another 0.5 of contributions in their DC account, which quite clearly illustrates the double burden they face in this case. But, while the assets accumulate in DC accounts, dividend and realized capital gains get taxed in period 2, which raises government revenue. Still, generation B and subsequent generations receive benefits that exceed their

contributions, while the government has more funds to allocate according to their budgetary plan.

Table 6: Transition from PAYG to hybrid scheme with capital gains taxes; IFR = 0.5

Period	Pillar/ Funding/ Taxes	Generation					Net Welfare Gen.	Net Welfare Gov.	Total Net Welfare
		A	B	C	D	E			
1	PAYG	1	-0.5						
	DC		-0.5				-0.5	0	-0.5
	Extra Cont.		-0.5						
2	PAYG		0.5	-0.5					
	DC		1.5	-0.5			1.0	0.5	1.5
	Tax		0.5						
3	PAYG			0.5	-0.5				
	DC			1.5	-0.5		1.0	0.5	1.5
	Tax			0.5					
4	PAYG				0.5	-0.5			
	DC				1.5	-0.5	1.0	0.5	1.5
	Tax				0.5				

Source: Oszarg/Stiglitz 2001, 24f, modified by the author

Table 7 explores a further design choice, which could include making generation B's accumulations tax-free to further enhance their incentive to contribute more to their pension savings. In this case, although their disposable income falls, over their lifetime, generation B still nets a welfare gain of 1.0 in period 2, just like subsequent cohorts, and the state still benefits from tax revenue on PAYG pensions and consumption without having to forego all income in period 2.

Table 7: Transition from PAYG to a hybrid scheme with capital gains taxes; B's accumulations are tax exempt; IFR = 0.5

Period	Pillar/ Funding/ Taxes	Generation					Net Welfare Gen.	Net Welfare Gov.	Total Net Welfare
		A	B	C	D	E			
1	PAYG	1	-0.5						
	DC		-0.5				-0.5	0	-0.5
	Extra Cont.		-0.5						
2	PAYG		0.5	-0.5					
	DC		2	-0.5			1.5	0	1.5
	Tax		0						
3	PAYG			0.5	-0.5				
	DC			1.5	-0.5		1.0	0.5	1.5
	Tax			0.5					
4	PAYG				0.5	-0.5			
	DC				1.5	-0.5	1.0	0.5	1.5
	Tax				0.5				

Source: Oszarg/Stiglitz 2001, 24f, modified by the author

These models show, that adding a funded component increases potential retirement benefits, but also incurs transition costs, which can be circumvented across multiple periods but cannot be entirely avoided. Admittedly, the transitioning generation must be willing to finance their

initial contributions with the guarantee in mind that they provide a stable retirement income for themselves. This incentive may be even more attractive, because individuals know that their own amount of contributions is only for themselves and further amplified the more they contribute. Also, in table 7, the assumed IFR was 0.5, which leads to a burdening twice as high for generation B. To minimize transition costs, further recommendations include implementing an IFR of 0.1 which increases with 0.1 steps over the next periods.

Table 8: Transition from PAYG to hybrid scheme with capital gains taxes; B's accumulations are tax exempt; IFR = 0.1, increasing with 0.1 steps over periods

Period	Pillar/ Funding/ Taxes	Generation					Net Welfare Gen.	Net Welfare Gov.	Total Net Welfare
		A	B	C	D	E			
1	PAYG	1	-0.9						
	DC		-0.1				-0.1	0	-0.1
	Extra Cont.		-0.1						
2	PAYG		0.8	-0.8					
	DC		0.4	-0.2			0.2	0	0.2
	Tax		0						
3	PAYG			0.7	-0.7				
	DC			0.6	-0.3		0.3	0.2	0.5
	Tax			0.2					
4	PAYG				0.6	-0.6			
	DC				0.9	-0.4	0.5	0.3	0.8
	Tax				0.3				

Source: Oszarg/Stiglitz 2001, 24f, modified by the author

Evidently, if using the total pension-contribution rate of 22.8% of gross earnings (BMSGPK 2025, 11) and the IFR of 10%, the extra contribution needed in the beginning would be 2.28%. This equals to a contribution rate of 25.08% for the transitioning generation, which is certainly a burden, but that higher contribution can be used to decrease the tax burden, thanks to the resulting lower taxable amount of earnings. In this case, transition costs are minimized and with the tax exemption for generation B's accumulations, they still experience a small net welfare gain, but one may conclude that the higher the extra contribution in the beginning, the higher the initial funded component and the higher the expected total net welfare gain for the whole population in period 2 and following.

There are a lot of other design choices to explore, like a transition financed by the state with different means, but as with the choice of more parameters in detail, as outlined in chapter 3.2.3 (OECD 2020, 102), further analysis is beyond the scope of this thesis. This modification of the simplified PAYG model from Oszarg und Stiglitz (1999, 12) in combination with the latest methodology used by Anarkulova et al. (2025, 2ff) and the calculations done by the OECD (2024, 86ff) may shine new light upon the expectations of using generally perceived riskier strategies to sustainably ensure adequate retirement income.

Further research is needed to assess the long-term effects of assumed time horizons and expected returns, alongside the various risks, such as mortality and labor risks, to which this hybrid system is exposed (Jarner et al. 2024, 815ff).

4.5 Resulting Challenges from the FPS Proposal

While implementing a funded component in the Austrian pension system using equity-heavy exposure default strategies is theoretically sound, as seen from the previous chapters, but several critical considerations remain:

First, in a time period of high public debt and constrained fiscal possibilities, these contribution-financed transition costs further strain public finances implicitly in the medium term, due to the foregone tax revenue (Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 50f). Especially now, during times where Austria's annual deficits reached new heights due to the government's management of public finances in recent years (Statistik Austria 2025b) one has to reconsider if this form of financing is feasible. However, it is important to remember that the future outcomes are beneficial for all involved generations and the state, even if policymakers would only strive for a small IFR as shown in table 8.

Second, without sound financial literacy levels the risk aversion of the general public to invest in short-term risky assets is too high to implement such a funded structure (Gomes et al. 2021, 16ff; OECD 2021, 7). This goes hand in hand with the historical data choosing relatively conservative strategies apparent through the data from voluntary plans by pension providers from 2023 pointed out in the chapters 4.2.1 (OECD 2024, 17ff).

Third, political and structural aversion from the financial intermediaries that are currently managing occupational or private pension schemes, might be high, which is intertwined with the second point made about the general financial literacy of the Austrian population (OECD 2021, 7ff).

Fourth, for a more regulatory-wise, detailed depiction and implementation regarding national law, this topic needs further research and is beyond the scope of this thesis.

5. Conclusion

This thesis introduced a proposal to implement an asset-backed pillar in the Austrian pension system due to the looming shortfalls presented by the statutory pension insurance.

The challenges that the Austrian pension system faces are twofold: First, the aging population has the effect that fewer contributors, e.g. people in employment come up with the necessary

benefits for the beneficiaries, e.g. pensioners. Therefore, with fewer contributions, combined with a rising number of eligible beneficiaries, this creates a challenge the current pension system cannot sustainably defy (Sinn 2000, 404). Second, with the first challenge in mind, federal funding requirements are increasing to bridge the shortfall of contributions, which in turn put a strain on public finances, not only because of subsidies in the first pillar but also due to other areas of the pension system where federal funding is needed (Mayrhuber 2025, 1ff).

To combat this challenges a multi-pillar approach was introduced, along with general recommendations and potential implementation pathways. In this thesis, such a pathway of a funded DC scheme, with quasi-public traits, involving the establishment of a new financial intermediary, similar to the existing "Pensionkassen" framework in Austria, was explored, based on Matsen and Thøgersen (2004, 884ff) and Jarner et al. (2024, 813ff). Generally, integrating multiple pension pillars in such a way achieves several key objectives simultaneously, laid out by the pension system requirements proposed by the World Bank (2008, 2f) and the OECD (2017, 87), while also spreading personal and systemic risks (Sinn 2000, 389). As a result, a multi-pillar system yields more robust and effective retirement outcomes than any single component could (Jarner et al. 2024, 832).

After conveying the proposal for the Austrian case and exploring different funding strategies, this thesis discussed viable design options. It became evident through the calculations of Anarkulova et al. (2025, 2ff) and the OECD (2024, 87ff) that an increase in the equity exposure would yield higher pre-retirement outcomes, with lower standard deviation than other strategies. These findings, when compared with the conservative asset allocations of existing pension plans, formulate that the funded component should not adopt an overly conservative approach and should pursue a less risk-averse strategy to ensure high enough retirement wealth outcomes.

Furthermore, the transition from a PAYG to a multi-pillar system can be challenging, especially in the face of difficult economic conditions, which raised questions about the feasibility and longevity of this proposal (Boulhol/Lüske 2019, 50). Regarding this matter, a PAYG model from Oszarg and Stiglitz (2001, 24f) was modified to fit the FPS proposal for the Austrian pension system. This model showed that transition costs cannot be entirely eliminated, but there are theoretical possibilities, e.g. exemption of the capital gains tax for assets from the transitioning generation or a lower IFR, to guarantee a minimization of these costs, while ensuring intergenerational fairness and equitable outcomes for generations to come. These possibilities are relying on the assumptions made in chapter 4.1 and the calculations and methodology by Anarkulova et al. (2025, 2ff) and the OECD (2024, 87ff).

Finally, given these findings, this proposal of a funded component for the Austrian pension system emerges as a promising and much needed solution to ensure intergenerational fairness and financial sustainability, but, admittedly, it remains a big leap from this theoretical design to a real-world implementation. This thesis has strived for interpretability over details; extended research is needed to go beyond this partial equilibrium approach to get more comprehensive answers. Further insights are needed not only with regard to the presented model, but also regarding asset allocation strategies in current funded pension schemes. Moreover, improving financial literacy will be essential to foster a better understanding of long-term risk-return trade-offs and to reduce political and structural resistance to investments in perceived as riskier assets.

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